

On the F.Smarandache LCM function $SL(n)$

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Abstract For any positive integer n , the famous F.Smarandache LCM function $SL(n)$ is defined as the smallest positive integer k such that $n \mid [1, 2, \dots, k]$, where $[1, 2, \dots, k]$ denotes the least common multiple of $1, 2, \dots, k$. The main purpose of this paper is using the elementary methods to study the mean value distribution property of $(P(n) - p(n))SL(n)$, and give an interesting asymptotic formula for it.

Keywords $SL(n)$ function, mean value distribution, asymptotic formula.

§1. Introduction and Result

For any positive integer n , the famous F.Smarandache LCM function $SL(n)$ defined as the smallest positive integer k such that $n \mid [1, 2, \dots, k]$, where $[1, 2, \dots, k]$ denotes the least common multiple of $1, 2, \dots, k$. For example, the first few values of $SL(n)$ are $SL(1) = 1$, $SL(2) = 2$, $SL(3) = 3$, $SL(4) = 4$, $SL(5) = 5$, $SL(6) = 3$, $SL(7) = 7$, $SL(8) = 8$, $SL(9) = 9$, $SL(10) = 5$, $SL(11) = 11$, $SL(12) = 4$, $SL(13) = 13$, $SL(14) = 7$, $SL(15) = 5$, \dots . From the definition of $SL(n)$ we can easily deduce that if $n = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \cdots p_r^{\alpha_r}$ be the factorization of n into primes powers, then

$$SL(n) = \max\{p_1^{\alpha_1}, p_2^{\alpha_2}, \dots, p_r^{\alpha_r}\}. \quad (1)$$

About the elementary properties of $SL(n)$, many people had studied it, and obtained some interesting results, see references [1], [2] and [3]. For example, Murthy [1] proved that if n be a prime, then $SL(n) = S(n)$, where $S(n)$ be the F.Smarandache function. That is, $S(n) = \min\{m : n \mid m!, m \in N\}$. Simultaneously, Murthy [1] also proposed the following problem:

$$SL(n) = S(n), \quad S(n) \neq n? \quad (2)$$

Le Maohua [2] solved this problem completely, and proved the following conclusion:

Every positive integer n satisfying (1) can be expressed as

$$n = 12 \quad \text{or} \quad n = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \cdots p_r^{\alpha_r} p,$$

where p_1, p_2, \dots, p_r, p are distinct primes and $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_r$ are positive integers satisfying $p > p_i^{\alpha_i}$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, r$.

Zhongtian Lv [3] studied the mean value properties of $SL(n)$, and proved that for any fixed positive integer k and any real number $x > 1$, we have the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{n \leq x} SL(n) = \frac{\pi^2}{12} \cdot \frac{x^2}{\ln x} + \sum_{i=2}^k \frac{c_i \cdot x^2}{\ln^i x} + O\left(\frac{x^2}{\ln^{k+1} x}\right),$$

where c_i ($i = 2, 3, \dots, k$) are computable constants.

Jianbin Chen [4] studied the value distribution properties of $SL(n)$, and proved that for any real number $x > 1$, we have the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{n \leq x} (SL(n) - P(n))^2 = \frac{2}{5} \cdot \zeta\left(\frac{5}{2}\right) \cdot \frac{x^{\frac{5}{2}}}{\ln x} + O\left(\frac{x^{\frac{5}{2}}}{\ln^2 x}\right),$$

where $\zeta(s)$ is the Riemann zeta-function, and $P(n)$ denotes the largest prime divisor of n .

Xiaoyan Li [5] studied the mean value properties of $P(n)SL(n)$ and $p(n)SL(n)$, and give two sharper asymptotic formulas for them, where $p(n)$ denotes the smallest prime divisor of n .

Yanrong Xue [6] defined another new function $SL^*(n)$ as follows: $SL^*(1) = 1$, and if $n = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \cdots p_r^{\alpha_r}$ be the factorization of n into primes powers, then

$$SL^*(n) = \min\{p_1^{\alpha_1}, p_2^{\alpha_2}, \dots, p_r^{\alpha_r}\}, \quad (3)$$

where $p_1 < p_2 < \cdots < p_r$ are primes.

It is clear that function $SL^*(n)$ is the dual function of $SL(n)$. So it has close relationship with $SL(n)$. About its elementary property of the function $SL^*(n)$, Yanrong Xue [6] proved the following conclusion:

For any positive integer n , there is no any positive integer $n > 1$ such that

$$\sum_{d|n} \frac{1}{SL^*(d)}$$

is an positive integer, where $\sum_{d|n}$ denotes the summation over all positive divisors of n .

In this paper, we shall study the value distribution properties of $(P(n) - p(n))SL(n)$, and give a sharper asymptotic formula for it. That is, we shall prove the following:

Theorem. For any real number $x > 1$ and any positive integer k , we have the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{n \leq x} (P(n) - p(n))SL(n) = \zeta(3) \cdot x^3 \cdot \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{b_i}{\ln^i x} + O\left(\frac{x^3}{\ln^{k+1} x}\right),$$

where $\zeta(s)$ is the Riemann zeta-function, $b_1 = \frac{1}{3}$, b_i ($i = 2, 3, \dots, k$) are computable constants.

§2. Proof of the theorem

In this section, we shall complete the proof of the theorem directly. For any positive integer $n > 1$, we consider the following cases:

A: $n = n_1 \cdot p$, $n_1 \leq p$, and $SL(n) = p$;

$B: n = n_2 \cdot p, n_2 > p, \text{ and } SL(n) = p;$

$C: n = m \cdot p^\alpha, \alpha \geq 2, \text{ and } SL(n) = p^\alpha;$

Now, for any positive integer $n > 1$, we consider the summation:

$$\sum_{n \leq x} (P(n) - p(n))SL(n).$$

It is clear that if $n \in A$, then from (1) we know that $SL(n) = p$. Therefore, by the Abel's summation formula (See Theorem 4.2 of [7]) and the Prime Theorem (See Theorem 3.2 of [8]):

$$\pi(x) = \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{a_i \cdot x}{\ln^i x} + O\left(\frac{x}{\ln^{k+1} x}\right),$$

where $a_i (i = 1, 2, \dots, k)$ are computable constants and $a_1 = 1$.

We have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ n \in A}} (P(n) - p(n))SL(n) &= \sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ n = n_1 \cdot p, n_1 \leq p \\ SL(n) = p}} (P(n) - p(n))SL(n) \\ &= \sum_{n_1 \leq \sqrt{x}} \sum_{n_1 \leq p \leq \frac{x}{n_1}} (P(n_1 \cdot p) - p(n_1 \cdot p))p \\ &= \sum_{n_1 \leq \sqrt{x}} \sum_{n_1 \leq p \leq \frac{x}{n_1}} (p - p(n_1))p \\ &= \sum_{n_1 \leq \sqrt{x}} \sum_{n_1 \leq p \leq \frac{x}{n_1}} p^2 - \sum_{n_1 \leq \sqrt{x}} \sum_{n_1 \leq p \leq \frac{x}{n_1}} p(n_1)p, \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

while

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n_1 \leq \sqrt{x}} \sum_{n_1 \leq p \leq \frac{x}{n_1}} p^2 &= \sum_{n_1 \leq \sqrt{x}} \left[\frac{x^2}{n_1^2} \pi\left(\frac{x}{n_1}\right) - \int_{n_1}^{\frac{x}{n_1}} 2y\pi(y)dy + O(n_1^3) \right] \\ &= \sum_{n_1 \leq \sqrt{x}} \left[\frac{x^3}{n_1^3} \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{b_i}{\ln^i \frac{x}{n_1}} + O\left(\frac{x^3}{n_1^3 \cdot \ln^{k+1} \frac{x}{n_1}}\right) \right] \\ &= \zeta(3) \cdot x^3 \cdot \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{b_i}{\ln^i x} + O\left(\frac{x^3}{\ln^{k+1} x}\right), \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

where $\zeta(s)$ is the Riemann zeta-function, $b_1 = \frac{1}{3}$, $b_i (i = 2, 3, \dots, k)$ are computable constants.

Note that $p(n_1) \leq n_1$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n_1 \leq \sqrt{x}} \sum_{n_1 \leq p \leq \frac{x}{n_1}} p(n_1)p &= \sum_{n_1 \leq \sqrt{x}} p(n_1) \sum_{n_1 \leq p \leq \frac{x}{n_1}} p \\ &= \sum_{n_1 \leq \sqrt{x}} p(n_1) \left[\frac{x}{n_1} \pi\left(\frac{x}{n_1}\right) - \int_{n_1}^{\frac{x}{n_1}} \pi(y)dy + O(n_1^2) \right] \\ &\ll \sum_{n_1 \leq \sqrt{x}} p(n_1) \cdot \frac{x^2}{n_1^2 \ln x} \ll \sum_{n_1 \leq \sqrt{x}} \frac{x^2}{n_1 \ln x} = O(x^2). \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

From (4), (5) and (6) we have

$$\sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ n \in A}} (P(n) - p(n))SL(n) = \zeta(3) \cdot x^3 \cdot \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{b_i}{\ln^i x} + O\left(\frac{x^3}{\ln^{k+1} x}\right), \quad (7)$$

where $b_1 = \frac{1}{3}$, b_i ($i = 2, 3, \dots, k$) are computable constants.

If $n \in B$, $SL(n) = p$, then by the Abel's summation formula and the Prime Theorem, we can deduce the following:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ n \in B}} (P(n) - p(n))SL(n) &= \sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ n = n_2 \cdot p, n_2 > p \\ SL(n) = p}} (P(n) - p(n))SL(n) \\ &= \sum_{\substack{n_2 \cdot p \leq x \\ n_2 > p}} (p - p(n_2))p \\ &\ll \sum_{\substack{n_2 \cdot p \leq x \\ n_2 > p}} p^2 = \sum_{p < \sqrt{x}} \sum_{p < n_2 \leq \frac{x}{p}} p^2 \\ &< \sum_{p < \sqrt{x}} \frac{x}{p} \cdot p^2 = \sum_{p < \sqrt{x}} x \cdot p \\ &= x \sum_{p < \sqrt{x}} p \ll x^2. \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

If $n \in C$, then $SL(n) = p^\alpha$, $\alpha \geq 2$. Therefore, using the Abel's summation formula and the Prime Theorem, we can obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ n \in C}} (P(n) - p(n))SL(n) &= \sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ n = m \cdot p^\alpha, \alpha \geq 2 \\ SL(n) = p^\alpha}} (P(n) - p(n))SL(n) \\ &= \sum_{\substack{m \cdot p^\alpha \leq x \\ \alpha \geq 2}} (P(m \cdot p^\alpha) - p(m \cdot p^\alpha))p^\alpha \\ &\ll \sum_{\substack{m \cdot p^\alpha \leq x \\ \alpha \geq 2}} p^{2\alpha} \ll \sum_{\substack{p^\alpha \leq x \\ \alpha \geq 2}} \sum_{m \leq \frac{x}{p^\alpha}} p^{2\alpha} \\ &\ll \sum_{\substack{p^\alpha \leq x \\ \alpha \geq 2}} \frac{x}{p^\alpha} \cdot p^{2\alpha} = \sum_{\substack{p^\alpha \leq x \\ \alpha \geq 2}} x \cdot p^\alpha \\ &= x \sum_{\substack{p^\alpha \leq x \\ \alpha \geq 2}} p^\alpha = x \sum_{\substack{p \leq x^{\frac{1}{\alpha}} \\ \alpha \geq 2}} p^\alpha \ll x^{\frac{5}{2}}. \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Now, combining (7), (8) and (9) we may immediately obtain the following asymptotic formula:

$$\sum_{n \leq x} (P(n) - p(n))SL(n) = \zeta(3) \cdot x^3 \cdot \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{b_i}{\ln^i x} + O\left(\frac{x^3}{\ln^{k+1} x}\right),$$

where $P(n)$ and $p(n)$ denote the largest and smallest prime divisor of n respectively, $\zeta(s)$ is the Riemann zeta-function, $b_1 = \frac{1}{3}$, b_i ($i = 2, 3, \dots, k$) are computable constants.

This completes the proof of Theorem.

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